

VIEWS OF SPIRITUALITY ON FINANCIAL DECISION MAKING

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Abstract - Spirituality is something that is beyond any religion. There is a famous saying that Religion divides but spirituality unites. The purpose of the study is to take note of different perceptions of spirituality and how it is related to finance. There is a growing body of research that provides strong empirical evidence that firms with spiritual values will perform better than those without (Mitroff and Benton, 1999, Jurkiewicz and Giacalone, 2004; Pandey and Gupta, 2008; Karakas, 2010; Gross and Holland 2011). Those firms have employees who are more loyal, productive, and innovative than other companies. This paper carries different views about spirituality and finance. The paper seeks to reveal the fact about the importance of spirituality while dealing with finance and investment options..

Index Terms - Spirituality, Religion, Finance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Spirituality is a word that carries a word 'Spirit' which means something inside us that cannot be seen but acts as a driving force accordingly we all act, feel, and make decisions. Many times people call it 'soul'. In the emerging era, the concept of spirituality has become increasingly popular among people, especially youth. Spirituality is concerned with a realization that there is a connection of oneself or soul with a higher self or soul. People nowadays are more driven by the purpose of a higher self or are more interested in finding the purpose.

Religion is a specific set of organized beliefs and practices, usually shared by a community or group. Emile Durkheim defined religion as "a unified system of beliefs and practices relative to sacred things, that is to say, things set apart and forbidden - beliefs and practices which unite into one single moral community called a church, all those who adhere to them". So religion is a different term from spirituality. Religion more or less involves certain practices but spirituality is concerned with the realization of oneself with a higher self.

II. FINANCIAL DECISION-MAKING AND SPIRITUALITY

Financial decision-making is an important and complex phenomenon. It involves a lot of factors including financial literacy which happens to be of the most importance. The term financial literacy is defined by (OECD) as "a combination of awareness, knowledge, skills, attitude, and behaviour necessary to make sound decisions and ultimately achieve individual financial well-being. According to (The Merriam-Webster dictionary, 1976) spirituality is "sensitivity or attachment to religious values and things of the spirit rather than material or worldly interest". So, when humans start doing things that will develop their connection with the supreme being, they will know how to effectively utilize the resources for better purposes.

Spirituality in financial decisions will restrict business players and individuals from indulging in fraudulent practices and other malpractices. In the presence of spirituality, there will be proper treatment as well as the realization of financial resources. Ethics and values will make the finances safe and secure. However, in the absence of these ethics and the spiritual nature of persons, there will be more corruption in the economy. The financial crisis in the year 2008, undoubtedly showed that values were absent in the culture of the USA. There have been so many works that show spirituality has an impact on making financial decisions to a greater extent. Whether it's about work-life decisions or business decisions adding spirituality will enhance its impact. A fundamental principle of finance is that the goal of the firm is the maximization of shareholder value. The basis for this is that the ultimate gauge of corporate success is the extent to which it increases the wealth of its shareholders. (Friedman, 2015).

SPIRITUALITY AND FINANCIAL DECISION

According to the work on (The study of Spirituality, Work Value, and Career Decision Making between Christian and non-christian College Students) by Huiling Peng and Mei-shuchen, the transcendent rationality orientation considers that man does not make career decisions based on the analysis of rational thought on the conscious level but rather based on some factors "beyond rational thought", nonlinear dynamics, such as religious belief, spirituality, calling and "meaning making" functions (Bloch, 2005; Constantine, Miville, Warren & Lewis-Coles, 2006; Dik & Duffy, 2009; Duffy & Blustein, 2005; Loder, 2005; Steger, Pickering, Shin, & Dik, 2010; Salsman, Brown, Brechting, & Carlson, 2005; Torrey & Duffy, 2012). In their studies, they have tried to show a positive relationship between spirituality and choice of work and further to know how spirituality helps in making the work more productive.

SPIRITUALITY IN WORKPLACE

The research paper by Charlene Litzsey was the view of Galen and West (1995) that says, a growing number of companies are setting off on spiritual journeys. It's not about bringing the religion into the office or requiring that employees chant mantras in their workstations. Rather the spirituality movement in the corporation is an attempt to create a sense of meaning and purpose at work and a connection between the company and its people.

SPIRITUALITY AND FINANCE

In an article, 'The science beneath spirituality and finance' by a columnist in 'Just in Time Guru', he shared his experience working at some investment firms. He quoted Albert Einstein, "What I see in nature is a magnificent structure that we can comprehend only very imperfectly, and that must fill a thinking person with a feeling of humility. This is a genuinely religious feeling that has nothing to do with mysticism". (Guru, 2016). He talks about the disequilibrium prevailing in an economy. Also, he cites this disequilibrium as the cause of the economic crisis and if there won't be any optimization of resources there will sooner be one more crisis. His article gives

the idea that a lack of values and ethics as a part of a very spiritual nature of a person can be disastrous in the long run if not in the short run.

SPIRITUALITY AND DECISIONS IN FINANCES LEAD TO SUCCESS

(Lagace, 2002) An article explores the fact that spirituality and success by interviewing some successful entrepreneurs and finding some positive relations between the two. For Robert Glassman, one of the successful entrepreneurs, his spirituality at work is expressed as a commitment to social justice. As a co-founder of and co-chairman of Wainwright Bank and Trust company based in Boston, Glassman (HBS MBA '69) said issues such as homelessness, Women's rights, and outreach to the gay and lesbian community have shaped his own life and the life of his business. In an interview with Jim Sharpe, CEO of Extrusion Technologies, he said he lives his values, and employees pick up on that instead of hiring new employees, he promoted existing employees to management roles. He believed that his employees had potential to work and his belief turned out to be true when some of them performed well. In one more conversation with an entrepreneur Gregory Slayton, chairman of Click Action Inc. He said the values he most often uses at work is the golden rule, the principle that people should do unto others as they would have others do unto them.

FINANCIAL PLANNING AND RELIGION

(Garvey, 2014) In her article, she says spiritual thinkers from Socrates to John Calvin advocated the importance of introspective familiarity in the pursuit of wisdom. According to her, everyone has their roots in values. In the field of finance, if one expresses their values to their clients or asks clients about their values, one can have a better relationship with their clients in the long run. In her words "Money should not be the key ingredient in our financial decisions. When strong values are present, ideally our financial life will reflect them. When your money is in service to your values, it becomes a supporting cast member of a show where your values play the lead". When values take the lead in our decision-making, our behaviour finally changes for good. Investment no longer causes insomnia, jobs support workers' lifestyles, and gratitude becomes a regular part of life. Clients will appreciate an advisor who cares for the whole person and advocates that kind of wellness. In her article, she gives us a clear idea to focus on the values that spirituality gives us rather than focusing on only wealth creation.

SPIRITUAL THINKERS CUM BUSINESSMAN'S VIEW ON SPIRITUALITY AND PROSPERITY

Choa Kok Sui (Samson Lim Choachuy), Filipino esotericist, Former chemical engineer, and businessman, He considered the founder of GMCKS Pranic-Healing and GMCKS Arhatic Yoga (GMCKS stands for Grand Master Choa Kok Sui). The soul develops by giving not by accumulating- MCKS Master has said that it is giving that we receive and that is the truth. It is like breathing. We need to exhale to inhale and inhale to exhale again. "You have to plant to harvest. When you give, it's like planting seeds. It comes back to you many, many times.", Master Choa Kok Sui.

It is a pure law of nature. We get what we give. What goes around comes around. So if we reverse it we can get what we want by giving the same things. That is why the master has emphasized character building. Tithing and service are a big part of character building. Master has always advised us to practice giving to receive. So if we want money, if we want to be wealthy, we need to give money. It is advisable to give about 10 percent of what we earn to charitable and spiritual causes. (Sui)

III. CONCLUSION

As we have discussed above different views on spirituality and finances by different research practitioners and scholars, it is evident that there has been a positive relationship between spirituality and financial decision-making. The impact of spirituality is not confined only to the financial decisions of a corporate enterprise but it influences the financial decisions of an individual too. We have also discussed religion and values and how religion and spirituality add something to our lives. In the last two articles, it was witnessed that spirituality can lead to a prosperous life and it can help people to stay calm in difficult situations in business and corporate affairs and their decisions were healthy and fair which led to success in their lives. The below quote also reveals the importance of spirituality in decision-making.

"I am never in control of what happens around me, but I am always in control of what happens within me"
"Marcy Herrera"

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